

**RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS: IMPACT OF COMORBIDITIES ON CLINICAL
PROGNOSIS OF COVID – 19 IN HOSPITALISED PATIENTS**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) presents with a wide spectrum of clinical severity, ranging from mild illness to life-threatening complications. Comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, cardiovascular and respiratory diseases have been shown to influence disease outcomes. Understanding their impact is essential for risk stratification and effective management of hospitalised patients. **Objective:** To evaluate the influence of pre-existing comorbidities on the clinical course, severity, and outcomes of COVID-19 among hospitalised patients. **Methods:** A retrospective observational study was conducted using medical records of confirmed COVID-19 patients admitted to tertiary care hospital with duration of 6 Months. Demographic details, comorbid conditions, laboratory findings, clinical severity, treatment interventions, and outcomes (recovery, ICU admission, or death) were analysed. Statistical associations between comorbidities and clinical outcomes were assessed using appropriate univariate and multivariate analyses. **Results:** Out of 150 hospitalised COVID-19 patients, 79 % had at least one comorbidity. Patients with multiple comorbidities exhibited significantly higher rates of ICU admission, prolonged hospital stay, and mortality ($p < 0.05$). Multivariate analysis identified diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease as independent predictors of poor prognosis. **Conclusion:** Comorbidities substantially worsen the clinical outcomes of hospitalised COVID-19 patients, with diabetes and cardiovascular diseases emerging as the strongest predictors of severity and mortality. Early identification and aggressive management of high-risk patients may improve survival and optimise healthcare resource utilisation.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19, comorbidities, retrospective analysis, clinical prognosis, hospitalised patients, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, mortality.

INTRODUCTION

Novel corona virus, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV2) is a newly emerging infection with ongoing pandemic causing significant mortality and morbidity.

Corona viruses are a large family of enveloped positive sense single stranded RNA viruses. The virus primarily affects the upper respiratory and gastrointestinal tracts. The entry of virus into host cells is mediated by transmembrane spike glycoprotein that forms the homotrimers protruding from the viral surface mediating receptor binding and proteolysis which leads to virus cell fusion. Angiotensin converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) is the cellular receptor for SARS CoV-2 while dipeptidyl peptidase 4 (DPP4) is the cellular receptor for MERS CoV.

The corona virus infection can be represented in three stages.

- Stage -1: The early infection phase
- Stage-2: The pulmonary phase
- Stage-3: The hyperinflammation phase

In the early stages, the patients generally present with symptoms such as fever, dry cough, fatigue, sputum production, sore throat, diarrhea and headache. Clinical signs include lymphopenia, elevated Interleukin-6, D-dimer and mild LDH levels.

In pulmonary phase, patients may develop shortness of breath, chest discomfort, fatigue, abnormal chest images and elevated transaminases.

In most advanced phases, some patients may develop cytokine storm which is the uncontrollable hyperinflammation phase that leads to other complications such as severe viral pneumonia complicated by respiratory failure, acute respiratory distress syndrome, shock, multiorgan failure and even death. Elevated inflammatory markers include CRP, LDH, IL-6, D-dimer, Ferritin, Troponin, NT-ProBNP are regarded as clinical hallmarks.

During COVID-19, the immune system plays a vital role correlating the degree of immune dysfunction with disease severity. Due to the infection, the immune system gets activated resulting in local inflammation by monocytes, dendritic cells, natural killers, T and B cells.

In case of severity, the accumulation of functional T and natural killer cells result in an inability to mount an effective antiviral immune response to clear SARS CoV – 2. Interleukin 6 levels remain elevated over time along with higher levels of tumor necrosis factor- α , macrophage inflammatory proteins, monocyte proteins result in systemic cytokine storm. Pre-existing chronic illnesses like diabetes, hypertension, hypothyroidism, COPD are independent risk factors for disease severity and death from COVID-19.

Many comorbidities associated with COVID-19 affect the functioning of immune system directly impacting the response.

Diabetes is a chronic disease which is characterized by abnormally elevated blood glucose levels due to impaired insulin action or insulin secretion. Type 1 diabetes is characterized by autoimmune mediated β -cells destruction, while type 2 diabetes is due to insulin resistance or insulin secretory defect. As diabetes increases susceptibility to infections, poorly controlled diabetes increases risk for gastrointestinal, urinary and respiratory tract infections characterised by chronic inflammation and impaired metabolism. This chronic inflammation leads to hyperinflammation developing cytokine storm.

Hyperglycaemia can also impair immune response increasing oxidative stress. In human monocytes, elevated glucose levels increase SARS CoV 2 replication and glycolysis sustain SARS CoV 2 replication producing reactive oxygen species and activating hypoxia inducible factor 1- α . Thus, hyperglycaemia might support viral proliferation.

In addition to disease aetiology, the treatment of diabetes may also have impact on COVID-19 prognosis. Dipeptidyl-peptidase 4 inhibitors that are commonly used for diabetes have an anti-inflammatory effect that reduces microphage infiltration, resulting in impaired immune response. Sodium glucose transporter 2 inhibitors indirectly increases risk by potentiating adverse effects. They also promote expression of angiotensin converting enzyme 2 to SARS CoV-2.

Hypertension, also known as high blood pressure is a condition in which persistently elevated arterial blood pressure is observed. It is the highest pre-existing comorbidity in COVID -19 patients. Uncontrolled blood pressure dysregulates the immune system making the CD8+ cells incapable of tackling viral infections.

Contributing to excess cytokine production. This down regulated immune system results in entry of virus easily into body. The virus thus enters and interacts with ACE2 receptors through its spike S protein gradually decreases ACE2 levels inducing adipose inflammation and implicates cytokine storm.

The use of renin-angiotensin aldosterone system inhibitors such as ACE inhibitors and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs) may also increase susceptibility to SARS CoV 2 infection. As ACE inhibitors and angiotensin receptor blockers increases the expression of ACE2, use of these medications may increase SARS CoV infection susceptibility.

DIAGNOSIS

COVID-19 ANTIGEN TEST

STANDARD Q COVID-19 Ag test is a rapid test to detect infection with 2019 new corona virus or SARS-CoV2. The test results are for clinical reference only and cannot be used as basis for confirming and excluding cases alone. Hence, CORADS and CTSI should also be considered to confirm the diagnosis of COVID-19.

Intended use

It is a rapid chromatographic immunoassay for the qualitative detection of specific antigen to SARS-CoV2 present in the human nasopharynx. It provides only an initial screening test result more specific alternative diagnostic method should be performed to confirm of SARS-CoV2 infection.

Test Principle

This test is based on capturing SARS-CoV2 antigen on to a color coded monoclonal anti-SARS-CoV2 antibody

coated line representing the sample and a separate control line. If SARS-CoV2 antigen is not present in the specimen, then no color appears on the test line. The control line should always appear whether the test is positive or negative and is a proof for proper test procedure.

Specimen

Swab from nasopharynx of the subject is taken and extracted into a buffer solution.

COVID-19 REPORTING AND DATA SYSTEM (CORADS)

Based on the CT findings, the level of suspicion for COVID-19 is graded from very low to high determining the severity of the disease. This is often combined with clinical findings to confirm the diagnosis.

Table – 1.

		CT FINDINGS
CO-RADS 1	NO	Normal or non-infectious abnormalities
CO-RADS 2	LOW	Abnormalities consistent with infections other than COVID - 19
CO-RADS 3	INTERMEDIATE	Unclear whether COVID-19 is present
CO-RADS 4	HIGH	Abnormalities suspicious for COVID-19
CO-RADS 5	VERY HIGH	Typical COVID-19
CO-RADS 6	PCR +	

CT SEVERITY INDEX: The CT scan is used to determine the pattern of the disease through imaging findings. The CT severity score is used to assess the changes in lung due to disease progression.

Table – 2.

SCORE	CT SEVERITY
< 10	MILD
11 – 20	MODERATE
21 – 30	SEVERE
31 – 40	CRITICAL

TREATMENT

- TAB. DOLO – Acetaminophen 650mg SOS
- TAB. LIMCEE – Ascorbic Acid 500mg BD
- TAB. VITNEURIN CZS – Multivitamin OD
- TAB. IVERLAST – Ivermectin 12mg OD
- CAP. DOXY – Doxycycline 100mg BD
- TAB. FAMOCID – Famotidine 40mg OD
- NANOFEROL – Vitamin D3 Once Weekly
- Methylprednisolone or Dexamethasone
- Enoxaparin sodium or Heparin
- Continue regular medications for Diabetes Mellitus, Hypertension, Thyroid and cardiac problems as before.

GENERAL ADVICE

- Strict home quarantine for 14 days
- Use face mask and gloves while handling things.
- Regular check for oxygen levels, if less than 92 needs hospitalization
- Regular healthy diet to be taken as before
- Steam inhalation twice daily.
- Avoid alcohol consumption
- Avoid smoking
- Gargle at regular intervals with Luke warm water for sore throat

DRUG REPURPOSING IN COVID-19

Medical experts have put all their effort to find out the cure for this infection and improve the quality of life of the patient's affected with this deadly corona virus. They used the concept of drug repurposing in treatment this viral infection.

Drug repurposing is a strategy used to discover new uses of approved drug. New medical indication of already existing drug is done.

The drugs used for repurposing are.

1. Chloroquine and Hydroxy-chloroquine

These are antimalarial drugs which are repurposed for use in COVID – 19. They act by blocking glycosylation of host receptor and break down the production of viral proteins by inhibiting endosomal pH. They also act as

immunomodulator by decreasing cytokine production and inhibit lysosomal activity. It was assumed that use of hydroxychloroquine as prophylaxis, prior to exposure of COVID – 19. But their administration had no beneficial effect.

2. Lopinavir/Rotinavir

A protease inhibitor used in HIV. These antiviral drugs are repurposed in COVID - 19. It is supposed to work against corona virus by inhibition of 3 chymotrypsin like protease. These drugs use is limited because adverse effects outweigh the benefits. There is no evidence of clinical benefit because it doesn't reduce the viral load in severe COVID - 19. In mild COVID – 19 cases the time of viral shedding is reduced and reduced time to alleviation of symptoms by inhibition of 3 chymotrypsin like protease, that disrupt the process of viral replication and release of viral particles from the host cells.

3. Famotidine

It is the antacid of choice in COVID - 19 patients. This histamine 2 receptor antagonist is effective in COVID - 19 because it also inhibits the 3 chymotrypsin like protease enzyme in the virus that is essential for replication of virus. It is beneficial in moderate to mild COVID - 19 infections.

4. Nafamostat and camostat

These are serine protease inhibitors which are approved in Japan for use in pancreatitis. It is tried in COVID – 19 because it blocks the entry of SARS-COV by acting as antagonist to serine protease TMPRSS2. Another benefit is due to its short acting anticoagulant effect which might be effective in inhibiting the intravascular coagulopathy in severe COVID – 19 patients.

5. Umifenovir

This antiviral is used in Russia and China against influenza virus. This act by inhibiting membrane fusion of virus, stimulating humoral immune response, stimulating phagocytosis, inducing interferon production. It might be effective in mild to moderate COVID - 19 infections but there is no proper evidence.

6. Nitazoxanide: It is an antiparasitic that is used in treatment of parasitic infections like *Giardia lamblia*, *Cryptosporidium parvum*, *Entamoeba histolytica*, *Ascaris lumbricoides*. Nitazoxanide was repurposed in influenza infection because of its efficacy against influenza virus that are resistant to neuraminidase inhibitors like oseltamivir. Now it is tried as repurpose drug in COVID – 19 as it blocks the maturation of viral capsid and protein that is essential for production of viral particles.

7. Ivermectin: This is an antiparasitic drugs which is used in scabies. In coronavirus it binds and stabilizes cell transported proteins used to enter nucleus. Ivermectin has long residence time in pulmonary tissue (three times more than that in plasma). It is import in

inhibitor. It converts RT PCR negative quickly in just a single dose.

8. Corticosteroids: Corticosteroid drugs are one of the blunt tools for suppressing the immune system by inhibiting the expression of repurpose drug many genes encoding the inflammatory mediators. They also decrease the cytokine storm that reduce the lung injury in ventilated patients. Dexamethasone and methylprednisolone are the most commonly used corticosteroids in COVID - 19. They should be used only in severe coronavirus infections when there is cytokine storm.

9. Interleukin 6 receptor antagonist: These are immunosuppressants drugs used in rheumatoid arthritis and systemic lupus erythematosus. Tocilizumab and sarilumab are used in cytokine storm syndrome in severe covid infection.

10. Baricitinib

This is a TNF alpha antagonist used in rheumatoid arthritis in Europe and US. It also acts blocking the JAK1 and JAK2. It is tried in moderate COVID – 19 pneumonia. It blocks viral entry and reduce organ damage.

11. Bevacizumab

It is a monoclonal antibody against the signaling protein VEGF. It is an angiogenesis inhibitor that suppresses the growth of tumor by inhibiting the blood supply to the tumor cell. In covid-19 by suppressing VEGF it reduces the amount of fluid entering the lungs in in patients with covid-19 infection. This drug should be used only in severe or critically severe COVID – 19 patients, with RR > 30/min, SPO2 < 93% on room air.

12. Fluvoxamine

It is a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor, an antidepressant used in OCD. It also binds to Sigma 1 receptor to shut down the signaling inflammatory cascade in in endoplasmic reticulum. That's it has a very strong anti-inflammatory property and also prevents cytokines storm. It reduces the requirement of ventilation and prevent severe breathing problems in in patients with mild COVID – 19.

13. Virafin

It is pegylated interferon alpha-2b. Virafin has been indicated for use in patients with moderate COVID-19, whose oxygen saturation is in the range 94-90%. Before it was repurposed for COVID-19, pegylated interferon alpha 2b was used to treat Hepatitis C. For the uninitiated, interferons are signalling proteins found in our bodies that act as immunological agents that help the body's immune system defend against viral infections. When the viral load is between moderate and high, the need for oxygen is rapid. So, by administering this medicine, the viral load will decrease, and the need for oxygen will also reduce. Virafin will reduce the severity

of the disease and perhaps be instrumental in reducing the mortality rates.

14.2-deoxy-D-glucose (2-DG)

Institute of Nuclear Medicine and Allied Sciences, a lab of DRDO in collaboration with Dr. Reddy's laboratories developed this drug for use in COVID-19. It was a potential cancer drug that has been approved for repurposing and is available as a sachet of powder that can be taken orally by dissolving it in water. It accumulates only the virus infected cells and stops viral synthesis and energy production. It helps on faster recovery of hospitalised patients and reduces Oxygen dependence. It showed faster symptomatic cure than standard of care in clinical trials.

COVID-19 VACCINATION: Vaccine is a substance prepared biologically to stimulate antibody production, providing acquired immunological response. They work by preparing the body's natural defences that is the immune system – to recognize and fight off the disease-causing viruses and bacteria they target. Vaccination is the term used when a vaccine is administered to stimulate the immune system against the disease. After vaccination, if the body is exposed to those disease-causing germs, the body will be able to destroy them, preventing illness.

As, vaccines are crucial tools in the battle against COVID-19, scientists across the world are collaborating and innovating to bring the best treatment and vaccines that will collectively help in saving lives and end this pandemic.

Several different types of potential vaccines for COVID-19 are under development, including.

- Inactivated or weakened virus vaccines, where a form of the virus that has been inactivated or weakened is used which doesn't cause disease but generates an immune response. Protein-based vaccines, which are harmless fragments of proteins or protein shells that mimic the COVID-19 virus to safely generate an immune response.
- Viral vector vaccines, are a safe virus that cannot cause disease but serves to produce coronavirus proteins to generate an immune response.
- RNA and DNA vaccines, are a cutting-edge approach that uses genetically engineered RNA or DNA to generate a protein that itself safely prompts an immune response.

Developing immunity through vaccination means that there will be a reduced risk of developing the illness and its consequences. This acquired immunity helps to fight the virus if exposed. This is particularly important to protect those who are at increased risk for severe illness from COVID-19, such as healthcare providers, older or elderly adults, and people with other medical conditions.

The vaccines that were authorized by at least one national regulatory authority for public use are.

1. **Comirnaty**, is an RNA vaccine produced by the German company BioNTech and the American company Pfizer.
2. **Vaxzevria** and **Covishield** are viral vector vaccines produced by the British University of Oxford, British-Swedish company AstraZeneca, and the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations.
3. **Sputnik V** is a viral vector vaccine produced by the Russian Gamaleya Research Institute of Epidemiology and Microbiology.
4. **BBIBP-CorV** is an inactivated virus vaccine produced by the China National Pharmaceutical Group (Sinopharm) and its Beijing Institute of Biological Products.
5. **Johnson & Johnson COVID** vaccine is a viral vector vaccine produced by Janssen Pharmaceutica (a subsidiary of Johnson & Johnson) and Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center.
6. **Moderna** is an RNA vaccine produced by the American company Moderna, the U.S. National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases, the U.S. Biomedical Advanced Research and Development Authority, and the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations.
7. **CoronaVac** is an inactivated virus vaccine produced by the Chinese company Sinovac Biotech.
8. **Covaxin** is an inactivated virus vaccine produced by the Indian company Bharat Biotech and the Indian Council of Medical Research.
9. **Convidicea** is a viral vector vaccine produced by the Chinese company CanSino Biologics and the Beijing Institute of Biotechnology of the Academy of Military Medical Sciences.
10. **EpiVacCorona** is a peptide vaccine produced by the Russian State Research Center of Virology and Biotechnology VECTOR.
11. **RBD-Dimer** is a subunit vaccine produced by the Chinese company Anhui Zhifei Longcom Biopharmaceutical.
12. **WIBP-CorV** is an inactivated virus vaccine produced by the China National Pharmaceutical Group (Sinopharm) and its Wuhan Institute of Biological Products.
13. **CoviVac** is an inactivated virus vaccine^[369] produced by the Chumakov Centre at the Russian Academy of Sciences.

Many vaccines were in different stages of development. Vaccines that are in human trials are.

- **Novavax** COVID-19 vaccine – subunit virus like particle.
- **Sanofi-GSK** COVID-19 vaccine – Subunit.
- **CureVac** COVID-19 vaccine – RNA(unmodified).
- **SOBERANA 02** – Conjugate subunit.
- **CIGB-66** – Subunit.

- **Chinese Academy COVID-19 vaccine** – Inactivated SARS-CoV-2.
- **QazCovid-in** – Inactivated SARS-CoV-2.
- **ZyCoV-D – DNA** - plasmid expressing SARS-CoV-2 S protein.
- **CoVLP** – Virus like particles.
- **SCB-2019** – Subunit.
- **COVIran Barakat** – Inactivated SARS-CoV-2.
- **UB-612** – Subunit.
- **GRAd-COV2** – Adenovirus vector.
- **West China Hospital COVID-19 vaccine** – Subunit.
- **MVC-COV1901** – Subunit.
- **Minhai COVID-19 vaccine** – Inactivated SARS-CoV-2.
- **DeINS1-2019-nCoV-RBD-OPT** – Viral vector.
- **Nanocovax** – Subunit.
- **Zhongyianke Biotech COVID – 19 vaccine** - Subunit.
- **Liaoning Maokangyuan Biotech COVID – 19 vaccine** – Subunit.
- **Walvax COVID-19 vaccine** – RNA.
- **ERUCOV-VAC** – Inactivated SARS-CoV-2.
- **INO-4800** – DNA vaccine.
- **AG0302-COVID-19** – DNA vaccine.
- **IIBR-100** – Vesicular stomatitis vector.
- **ARCT-021** – RNA.
- **VBI-2909** – Virus like particle.
- **NDV-HXP-S** – VIRAL VECTOR.
- **Sanofi-Translate Bio COVID-19 vaccine** – RNA.
- **COVIVAC** – Viral vector.
- **EuCorVac-19** – Subunit.
- **RBD SARS-CoV-2 HBsAg VLP** – Virus like particle.
- **GX-19 (GX-19N)** – DNA vaccine.
- **AV-COVID-19** – Viral vector.
- **VLA2001** – Inactivated SARS-CoV-2.
- **TAK-919** – RNA.
- **TAK-019** – Subunit.
- **COVID-eVax** – DNA.
- **ChulaCov19** – RNA.
- **COVID-19/Aapc** – Viral vector.
- **LV-SMENP-DC** – Viral vector.
- **ImmunityBio COVID-19 vaccine** – Viral vector.
- **COVAX-19** – Subunit.
- **HGC019** – RNA.
- **Bio E COVID-19 (BECOV2D)** – Subunit.
- **Bangavax** – RNA.
- **PTX-COVID - 19-B** – RNA.
- **COVAC-2** – Subunit..
- **AdCOVID** – Viral vector.
- **VXA-CoV2-1** – Viral vector.
- **AdCLD-CoV19** – Viral vector.
- **SpFN COVID-19 Vaccine** – Subunit.
- **MVA-SARS-2-S** – Viral vector.
- **ReCOV** – Subunit.
- **DeINS1-nCoV-RBD LAIV** – Virus like particle.

In India, three vaccines have been granted emergency use authorization by the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO).

1. COVISHIELD which is AstraZeneca's vaccine manufactured by Serum Institute of India and is a Viral Vector-based.

Composition: Inactivated adenovirus with segments of Coronavirus, Aluminium Hydroxide Gel, L-Histidine, L-Histidine Hydrochloride Monohydrate, Magnesium Chloride Hexahydrate, Polysorbate 80, Ethanol, Sucrose, Sodium Chloride, and Disodium Edetate Dihydrate (EDTA).

2. COVAXIN which is manufactured by Bharat Biotech Limited and is a Whole-virion Inactivated Coronavirus Vaccine.

Composition: Inactivated Coronavirus, Aluminum Hydroxide Gel, TLR 7/8 Agonist, 2-Phenoxyethanol and Phosphate Buffered Saline [NKA1].

3. SPUTNIK V which is a vector-based vaccine made by the Gamaleya Research Institute of Epidemiology and Microbiology in Moscow.

Composition: Tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane, Sodium chloride, Sucrose, Magnesium Chloride hexahydrate, Disodium EDTA dihydrate, Polysorbate 80, Ethanol 95%, Water.

Adequate immune response was observed 2-3 weeks after completion of entire vaccination schedule i.e., after the second doses.

Even though, vaccines are designed for immunity without the dangers of getting the diseases, it is common to experience some mild-to-moderate side effects. This is due to the immune system which increases blood flow so more immune cells can circulate raising body temperature in order to kill the virus.

Reported side effects to COVID-19 vaccines are mostly been mild to moderate and short- lasting. They include.

- ◆ Fever
- ◆ Fatigue
- ◆ Headache
- ◆ Muscle Pain
- ◆ Chills
- ◆ Diarrhoea
- ◆ Pain at the injection site

After vaccination, for the first fourteen days, there will be no significant levels of protection, as it usually takes a few weeks for the body to build immunity against SARS-CoV-2, hence the person could be infected with SARS-CoV-2 just before or after vaccination and still get sick with COVID-19.

Safe and effective vaccines will be revolutionary; but for the anticipated future we must continue wearing masks maintaining social distancing and avoiding crowds. Being vaccinated does not mean that we can throw

caution to the wind and put ourselves and others at risk, particularly because it is still not clear the degree to which the vaccines can protect not only against disease but also against infection and transmission.

PRONE POSITIONING

Prone positioning refers to the technique of patient lying on their abdomen facing down which helps the patient to breathe better. It has been used in mechanically ventilated patients with severe acute respiratory distress syndrome. It is generally used for sedative patients but is more beneficial in awake patients of COVID-19.

Benefits of prone positioning

Prone positioning improves lung function as the lung compression is less when lied on stomach. With this improved lung function, less support from ventilator is required and thus reduces risk of ventilator induced lung injury. This positioning improves heart pumping resulting in improved oxygen delivery to body and also helps to redistribute blood and air flow more evenly enhancing gas exchange.

Secretions produced due to lung disease were drained better while on prone position as mouth and nose are facing down.

Side effects

- ◆ Facial edema
- ◆ Airway obstruction
- ◆ Skin lesions
- ◆ Difficulties with enteral feeding
- ◆ Transitory decrease in oxygen saturation
- ◆ Hypotension
- ◆ Arrhythmias
- ◆ Loss of venous accesses and probesLoss of dialysis drains and catheters accidental extubation.
- ◆ Apical atelectasis due to incorrect positioning of the tracheal tube.
- ◆ Increased need for sedation.

METHODOLOGY

Study site: Studies carried out at Tertiary Care Hospital, Kakinada.

Study Duration: Six months

Sample size: 150 cases

Study Design: A retrospective observational study

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of all age groups and gender
- Patients with diabetes and hypertension
- Patients who were diagnosed clinically with COVID – 19
- Patients who were diagnosed with diabetes or hypertension during hospitalization

Exclusion criteria

- Patients with other comorbidities than diabetes and hypertension
- Patients who were treated on OPD basis

Source of data collection

collected from the case sheets of patients admitted and treated in the hospital.

Method of data collection

- Patient demographics like age, gender, past medical history, patient's vitals, etc. were collected in a specially designed data collection form.
- Lab parameters such as COVID-19 inflammatory markers, blood glucose levels, Serum electrolytes, liver function tests, renal function tests, CT scan findings assessed during admission, therapy and discharge were note in the data collection form.
- All the details regarding the medications used along with the doses, dosage form and frequency were noted.
- Information about oxygenation, convalescent plasma therapy, anti-viral therapy, anticoagulant therapy, steroid therapy, length of stay and intensive care about each patient was examined and noted.
- The clinical outcomes such as discharge, referring to higher centers, OP based therapy, death was noted.
- If discharged, data regarding home oxygenation, SPO2 level, discharge medications were mentioned in data collection form.

Uses

- Identifying the key- evidence based prognostic factors in order to improve outcomes of COVID-19 patients.
- Estimating the burden of comorbidities on COVID-19 patients.
- Researching the effectiveness of repurposed drugs used in therapy.
- Monitoring and comparing comorbidities effect on COVID-19.
- Monitoring and identifying drug related effects and their management.
- Helping for precise management of patients with comorbidities.

Limitations

- The survey does not take into consideration comorbidities other than diabetes and hypertension.
- The survey may overestimate or underestimate the likelihood of mortality as socio- demographic characteristics may vary.
- This study didn't include pediatric patients.
- The clinical outcome for patients referred or transferred to higher centers was not included.

Statistical method used

By using IBM SPSS Software, Mean values were calculated for age, gender, length of stay, treatment, lab parameters. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and

percentage were also calculated and bar graphs, pie charts and clustered graphs were obtained.

Ethical committee clearance

Institutional ethical committee approved our study. It doesn't involve any administration of drugs to humans or

animals and as there is no collection of specimen or serum samples, informed consent form was collected from the patients to collect the data.

RESULTS

Table-3: Socio-Demographic & Clinical Characteristics of COVID-19 patients.

S.No	VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	Gender		
	Male	103	68.7
	Female	47	31.3
2.	Age		
	Below 41 years	22	14.7
	41-60 years	66	44
	Above 60 years	62	41.3
3.	No comorbidities		
		53	35.3
4.	Diabetes		
	Yes	21	14
5.	Hypertension		
	Yes	32	21.3
6.	Diabetes + Hypertension		
	Yes	39	26
7.	Length of stay		
	Below a week	40	26.7
	7-14 days	94	62.7
	Above two weeks	16	10.6
8.	Intensive Care		
	Yes	53	35.3
	No (Room)	97	64.7
9.	Convalescent Plasma		
	Yes	20	13.3
10.	Steroid dosage		
	Less than 1 mg/kg	25	16.7
	1-4 mg/kg	102	68
	More than 4 mg/kg	23	15.3
11.	Anti-viral therapy		
	Not given	25	16.7
	Remdesivir	119	79.3
	Favipiravir	6	4
12.	Oxygenation		
	Not required	81	54
	Oxygen Mask	51	34
	NIV	11	73.3
	HFNC	3	2
	Ventilator	4	2.7
13.	Outcome		
	Discharge	133	88.7
	Higher Center	11	7.3
	Death	6	4

Table- 4: Clinical Statistics Of COVID-19 Patients.

		No Comorbidities	Hypertension	Diabetes Mellitus	Diabetes Mellitus+ Hypertension	Others
Gender	Male	37(70%)	24(75%)	12(57%)	28(72%)	2
	Female	16(30%)	8(25%)	9(43%)	11(28%)	3
Age	≤ 40	18(34%)	2 (6%)			2
	41-60	23(43%)	10(31%)	10(48%)	21(54%)	2
	>60	12(22%)	20(63%)	11(52%)	18(46%)	1
Length of stay	≤ 7 days	18(34%)	10(31%)	3(14%)	6(15%)	3
	8-14 days	30(57%)	19(60%)	13(62%)	30(77%)	2
	>14 days	5(9%)	3(9%)	5(24%)	3(8%)	
ICU/ Room	ICU	16(30%)	11(34%)	10(48%)	14(36%)	2
	Room	37(70%)	21(66%)	11(52%)	25(64%)	3
Anti-viral therapy	Remdesivir	39(74%)	25(78%)	16(76%)	37(95%)	2
	Favipiravir	3(5%)	1(3%)	1(5%)		1
	Not given	11(21%)	6(19%)	4(19%)	2(5%)	2
Convalescent Plasma		7(13%)	7(22%)	3(14%)	2(5%)	1
Steroid dosage	< 1 mg/kg	10(19%)	5(15%)	4(19%)	5(13%)	1
	1-4 mg/kg	32(60%)	22(69%)	14(67%)	30(77%)	4
	> 4 mg/kg	11(21%)	5(16%)	3(14%)	4(10%)	
Oxygenation	Oxygen mask	7(13%)	14(44%)	10(48%)	19(49%)	1
	NIV	4 (7%)	1(3%)	2(9%)	3(7%)	1
	HFNC	3 (6%)				
	Ventilator	2(4%)	1(3%)		1(3%)	
	Not required	37(70%)	16(50%)	9(43%)	16(41%)	3
Outcome	Discharge	50(94%)	28(88%)	19(90%)	32(82%)	4
	Higher center		3(9%)	1(5%)	6(15%)	1
	Death	3(6%)	1(3%)	1(5%)	1(3%)	
CRP	Admission	48.6	45.5	45.6	53.2	37
	During Therapy	29.5	27.3	30.1	38.2	11
	Discharge	13.2	10.2	18.9	25.9	11
D- Dimer		318.6	342	388	372	344
Ferritin		281.4	599	307	265	278
LDH		576.6	586	603	553	405
IL-6		41.6	23	74	35	22
CTSI		13	13	14	15	13

**NO COMORBODITIES
GENDER
Table – 5.**

	Frequency	Percentage
Male	37	69.8
Female	16	30.2
Total	53	100.0

Fig-1: Gender distribution in no – comorbidities patients.

AGE

Table – 6.

	Frequency	Percentage
Below 41 years	18	34.0
41-60 years	23	43.4
Above 60 years	12	22.6
Total	53	100.0

Fig-2: Age distribution in no – comorbidities patients.

LENGTH OF STAY

Table - 7

	Frequency	Percentage
Below 8 days	18	34.0
8 - 14 days	30	56.6
Above 14 days	5	9.4
Total	53	100.0

Fig-3: Length of Stay in no – comorbidities patients.

ICU OR ROOM

Table – 8.

	Frequency	Percentage
ICU	16	30.2
Room	37	69.8
Total	53	100.0

Fig-4: Intensive Care in no – comorbidities patients.

STEROID DOSAGE

Table - 9

	Frequency	Percentage
< 1 mg/kg	10	18.9
1 - 4 mg/kg	32	60.4
> 4 mg/kg	11	20.8
Total	53	100.0

Fig-5: Steroid Dosage in no – comorbidities patients.

ANTI-VIRAL THERAPY

Table – 10.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not given	11	20.8
Remdesivir	39	73.6
Favipiravir	3	5.7
Total	53	100.0

Fig-6: Anti-viral Therapy in no – comorbidities patients.

OXYGENATION

Table – 11.

	Frequency	Percentage
Oxygen mask	7	13.2
NIV	4	7.5
HFNC	3	5.7
Ventilator	2	3.8
Total	53	100.0

Oxygenation

Fig-7: Oxygen Therapy in no – comorbidities patients.

CRP LEVELS

Table – 12.

	CRP at admission	CRP during therapy	CRP at discharge
Mean	48.5920	29.4711	13.2438

DIMER, FERRITIN, LDH, IL-6, CTSI

Table – 13.

	D-Dimer	Ferritin	LDH	Interleukin - 6	CTSI
Mean	318.6150	281.3769	576.6498	41.6388	13.14

OUTCOME

Table – 14

	Frequency	Percentage
Discharge	50	94.3
Death	3	5.7
Total	53	100.0

Fig-8: Outcome in no – comorbidities patients.

**HYPERTENSION
GENDER**
Table – 15.

	Frequency	Percentage
Male	24	75.0
Female	8	25.0
Total	32	100.0

Fig-9: Gender distribution in hypertensive patients.

AGE
Table – 16.

	Frequency	Percentage
Below 41 years	2	6.3
41-60 years	10	31.3
Above 60 years	20	62.5
Total	32	100.0

Fig-10: Age distribution in hypertensive patients.

LENGTH OF STAY
Table – 17.

	Frequency	Percentage
Below 8 days	10	31.3
8 - 14 days	19	59.4
Above 14 days	3	9.4
Total	32	100.0

Fig-11: Length of Stay in hypertensive patients.

ICU OR ROOM
Table – 18.

	Frequency	Percentage
ICU	11	34.4
Room	21	65.6
Total	32	100.0

Fig-12: Intensive Care in hypertensive patients.

STEROID DOSAGE
Table – 19.

	Frequency	Percentage
< 1 mg/kg	5	15.6
1 - 4 mg/kg	22	68.8
> 4 mg/kg	5	15.6
Total	32	100.0

Fig-13: Steroid Dosage in hypertensive patients.

ANTI-VIRAL THERAPY

Table – 20.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not given	6	18.8
Remdesivir	25	78.1
Favipiravir	1	3.1
Total	32	100.0

Anti-viral Therapy

Fig-14: Anti-viral Therapy in hypertensive patients.

OXYGENATION

Table – 21.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not required	16	50.0
Oxygen mask	14	43.8
NIV	1	3.1
Ventilator	1	3.1
Total	32	100.0

Oxygenation

Fig-15: Oxygenation in hypertensive patients.

CRP LEVELS

Table – 22

	CRP at admission	CRP during therapy	CRP at discharge
Mean	45.4574	27.3346	10.2243

D-DIMER, FERRITIN, LDH, IL-6, CTSI

Table – 23

	D-Dimer	Ferritin	LDH	Interleukin - 6	CTSI
Mean	342.0778	299.3450	586.9079	23.4761	13.29

OUTCOME
Table – 24.

	Frequency	Percentage
Discharge	28	87.5
Higher Center	3	9.4
Death	1	3.1
Total	32	100.0

Fig-16: Clinical Outcomes in hypertensive patients.

DIABETES MELLITUS
GENDER
Table – 25.

	Frequency	Percentage
Male	12	57.1
Female	9	42.9
Total	21	100.0

Fig-17: Gender distribution in diabetic patients.

AGE
Table – 26.

	Frequency	Percentage
41-60 years	10	47.6
Above 60 years	11	52.4
Total	21	100.0

Fig-18: Age distribution in diabetic patients.

LENGTH OF STAY

Table – 27.

	Frequency	Percentage
Below 8 days	3	14.3
8 - 14 days	13	61.9
Above 14 days	5	23.8
Total	21	100.0

Fig-19: Length of Stay in diabetic patients.

ICU OR ROOM

Table – 28.

	Frequency	Percentage
ICU	10	47.6
Room	11	52.4
Total	21	100.0

Fig-20: Intensive Care in diabetic patients.

STEROID DOSAGE

Table – 29.

	Frequency	Percentage
< 1 mg/kg	4	19.0
1 - 4 mg/kg	14	66.7
> 4 mg/kg	3	14.3
Total	21	100.0

Fig-21: Steroid Dosage in diabetic patients.

ANTI-VIRAL THERAPY

Table – 30.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not given	4	19.0
Remdesivir	16	76.2
Favipiravir	1	4.8
Total	21	100.0

Fig-22: Anti-viral Therapy in diabetic patients.

OXYGENATION

Table – 31.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not required	9	42.9
Oxygen mask	10	47.6
NIV	2	9.5
Total	21	100.0

Fig-23: Oxygenation in diabetic patients.

CRP LEVELS

Table – 32.

	CRP at admission	CRP during therapy	CRP at discharge
Mean	45.6750	30.1389	18.8765

D-DIMER, FERRITIN, LDH, IL-6, CTSI

Table – 33.

	D-Dimer	Ferritin	LDH	Interleukin - 6	CTSI
Mean	388.1950	307.5000	603.8953	74.6991	14.60

OUTCOME

Table – 34.

	Frequency	Percentage
Discharge	19	90.5
Higher Center	1	4.8
Death	1	4.8
Total	21	100.0

Fig-24: Clinical Outcomes in diabetic patients.

DIABETES MELLITUS + HYPERTENSION

GENDER

Table – 35

	Frequency	Percentage
Male	28	71.8
Female	11	28.2
Total	39	100.0

Fig-25: Gender distribution in Patients with Both DM+HTN.

AGE

Table – 36.

	Frequency	Percentage
41-60 years	21	53.8
Above 60 years	18	46.2
Total	39	100.0

Fig-26: Age distribution in Patients with Both DM+HTN.

LENGTH OF STAY

Table – 37

	Frequency	Percentage
Below 8 days	6	15.4
8 - 14 days	30	76.9
Above 14 days	3	7.7
Total	39	100.0

Fig-27: Length of Stay in Patients with Both DM+HTN.

ICU OR ROOM

Table – 38.

	Frequency	Percentage
ICU	14	35.9
Room	25	64.1
Total	39	100.0

Fig-28: Intensive care in Patients with Both DM+HTN.

STEROID DOSAGE

Table – 39.

	Frequency	Percentage
< 1 mg/kg	5	12.8
1 - 4 mg/kg	30	76.9
> 4 mg/kg	4	10.3
Total	39	100.0

Fig-29: Steroid Dosage in Patients with Both DM+HTN.

ANTI-VIRAL THERAPY

Table – 40.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not given	2	5.1
Remdesivir	37	94.9
Total	39	100.0

Fig-30: Anti-viral Therapy in Patients with Both DM+HTN.

OXYGENATION

Table – 41.

	Frequency	Percentage
Not required	16	41.0
Oxygen mask	19	48.7
NIV	3	7.7
Ventilator	1	2.6
Total	39	100.0

Oxygenation
Fig-31: Oxygenation in Patients with Both DM+HTN.

CRP LEVELS

Table – 42.

	CRP at admission	CRP during therapy	CRP at discharge
Mean	53.2241	38.2487	25.9462

D-DIMER, FERRITIN, LDH, IL-6, CTSI

Table – 43.

	D-Dimer	Ferritin	LDH	Interleukin - 6	CTSI
Mean	372.1586	265.8278	553.8533	35.9678	15.20

OUTCOME

Table – 44

	Frequency	Percentage
Discharge	32	82.1
Higher Center	6	15.4
Death	1	2.6
Total	39	100.0

Outcome
Fig-32: Clinical Outcome in Patients with Both DM+HTN.

COMPARISON OF DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS BETWEEN COVID-19 PATIENTS

Table – 45

	< 41 years	41 – 60 years	> 60 years
No Comorbidities	18 (34%)	23 (43%)	12 (22%)
Hypertension	2 (6%)	10 (31%)	20 (63%)
Diabetes Mellitus	-	10 (48%)	11 (52%)
DM + HTN	-	21 (54%)	18 (46%)
Others	2 (40%)	2 (40%)	1 (20%)
Total	22	66	62

Clustered Bar Count of Age by Comorbidities

Fig-33: Comparison of ages between COVID-19 Patients.

Table – 46.

	MALE	FEMALE
No Comorbidities	37 (70%)	16 (30%)
Hypertension	24 (75%)	8 (25%)
Diabetes Mellitus	12 (57%)	9 (43%)
DM + HTN	28 (72%)	11 (28%)
Others	2 (40%)	3 (60%)
Total	103	47

Clustered Bar Count of Gender by Comorbidities

Fig-34: Comparison of genders between COVID-19 Patients.

Table – 47.

	< 8 DAYS	8 – 14 DAYS	> 14 DAYS
No Comorbidities	18 (34%)	30 (57%)	5 (9%)
Hypertension	10 (31%)	19 (60%)	3 (9%)
Diabetes Mellitus	3 (14%)	13 (62%)	5 (24%)
DM + HTN	6 (15%)	30 (77%)	3 (8%)
Others	3 (60%)	2 (40%)	-
Total	40	94	16

Clustered Bar Count of Length Of Stay by Comorbidities

Fig-35: Comparison of length of stay between COVID-19 Patients.

Table – 48.

	ICU	ROOM
No Comorbidities	16 (30%)	37 (70%)
Hypertension	11 (34%)	21 (66%)
Diabetes Mellitus	10 (48%)	11 (52%)
DM + HTN	14 (36%)	25 (64%)
Others	2 (40%)	3 (60%)
Total	53	97

Clustered Bar Count of ICU or Room by Comorbidities

Fig-36: Comparison of intensive care between COVID-19 Patient.

Table – 49.

	< 1 mg/kg	1 – 4 mg/kg	> 4 mg/kg
No Comorbidities	10 (19%)	32 (60%)	11 (21%)
Hypertension	5 (15%)	22 (69%)	5 (16%)
Diabetes Mellitus	4 (19%)	14 (67%)	3 (14%)
DM + HTN	5 (13%)	30 (77%)	4 (10%)
Others	1 (20%)	4 (80%)	-
Total	25	102	23

Clustered Bar Count of Steroid Dosage by Comorbidities

Fig-37: Comparison of steroid dosage between COVID-19 Patients.

Table – 50.

	Remdesivir	Fapiravir	NO
No Comorbidities	39 (74%)	3 (5%)	11 (21%)
Hypertension	25 (78%)	1 (3%)	6 (19%)
Diabetes Mellitus	16 (76%)	1 (5%)	4 (19%)
DM + HTN	37 (95%)	-	2 (5%)
Others	2 (40%)	1 (20%)	2 (40%)
Total	119	6	25

Clustered Bar Count of Anti-viral Therapy by Comorbidities

Fig-38: Comparison of anti-viral therapy between COVID-19 Patients.

Table – 51.

	OXYGEN MASK	HFNC	NIV	VENTILATOR	NO
No Comorbidities	7 (13%)	3 (6%)	4 (7%)	2 (4%)	37 (70%)
Hypertension	14 (44%)	-	1 (3%)	1 (3%)	16 (50%)
Diabetes Mellitus	10 (48%)	-	2 (9%)	-	9 (43%)
DM + HTN	19 (49%)	-	3 (7%)	1 (3%)	16 (41%)
OTHERS	1 (20%)	-	1 (20%)	-	3 (60%)
Total	51	3	11	4	81

Fig-39: Comparison of oxygenation between COVID-19 patients.

Table – 52.

	CRP - 1	CRP - 2	CRP - 3
No Comorbidities	48.59	29.47	13.31
Hypertension	45.45	27.83	10.22
Diabetes Mellitus	45.67	30.13	15.80
DM + HTN	53.22	38.24	25.96
Others	37.15	11.85	11.62

Fig-40: Comparison of CRP levels – at admission, during therapy and at discharge between COVID-19 patients.

Table – 53.

	D-DIMER
No Comorbidities	318.615
Hypertension	342.077
Diabetes Mellitus	388.195
DM + HTN	372.169
Others	344.5

Fig-41: Comparison of D - Dimer levels between COVID-19 patients.

Table – 54

	Ferritin
No Comorbidities	281.37
Hypertension	299.34
Diabetes Mellitus	307.5
DM + HTN	318.99
Others	278.7

Fig-42: Comparison of Ferritin levels between COVID-19 patients.

Table – 55.

	LDH
No Comorbidities	576.64
Hypertension	586.90
Diabetes Mellitus	603.89
DM + HTN	553.85
Others	405.47

Fig-43: Comparison of LDH levels between COVID-19 patients.

Table – 56.

	IL -6
No Comorbidities	41.63
Hypertension	24.017
Diabetes Mellitus	74.60
DM + HTN	35.96
Others	22.65

Fig-44: Comparison of Interleukin – 6 levels between COVID-19 patients

Table – 57.

	CTSI
No Comorbidities	13
Hypertension	13
Diabetes Mellitus	14
DM + HTN	15
Others	16

Fig-45: Comparison of CTSI score between COVID-19 patients.

Table – 58.

	DISCHARGE	HIGHER CENTER	DEATH
No Comorbidities	50 (94%)	-	3 (6%)
Hypertension	28 (88%)	3 (9%)	1 (3%)
Diabetes Mellitus	19 (90%)	1 (5%)	1 (5%)
DM + HTN	32 (82%)	6 (15%)	1 (3%)
OTHERS	4 (80%)	1 (20%)	-
Total	133	11	6

Fig-46: Comparison of Clinical outcomes between COVID-19 patients.

DISCUSSION

A total of **150** patients were hospitalized due to COVID-19 infection in Siddhartha Hospital, Kakinada. **6** patients died during hospitalization; **133** patients were discharged while **11** patients were referred to higher Center for treatment.

Of total **150** patients, most of the effected were in the age 41-60 years i.e., **66** patients (**44%**). **22** patients (**15%**) were below 41 years and **62** patients (**41%**) were above 60 years of age. Most patients were of male gender that is **103** patients (**69%**) and the female were **47** in number (**31%**).

Length of stay in majority of patients i.e., **94** patients (**63%**) was observed to be 8- 14 days. **40** patients (**27%**) stayed below one week while 16 patients (**10%**) stayed for more than 2 weeks. **97** patients (**65%**) were treated in room while **53** patients (**35%**) required intensive care.

For maximum of the patients [**119** (**79%**)], Remdesivir was administered and **6** patients (**4%**) received Favipiravir. Out of **150**, **20** patients received convalescent plasma. In order to suppress severe inflammatory reactions, steroids such as Dexamethasone and Methyl prednisolone were used.

For accurate analysis, Dexamethasone dose was equated to methylprednisolone. Of all **150** patients, **102** patients (**68%**) received 1-4 mg/kg of systemic steroid dose, while **25** patients (**17%**) received less than 1mg/kg and **23** patients (**15%**) received more than 4mg/kg.

Mechanical ventilation was given for **4** patients, none of them survived. Oxygen through high flow nasal canula was given for **3** patients (**2%**); **11** patient (**7%**) received oxygen through NIV and **51** patients (**34%**) received oxygen through oxygen mask.

The mean values of C-reactive protein levels for patient at the time of admission, during therapy and at discharge are: **46 ug/ml**, **27.2 ug/ml**, **15.8 ug/ml** respectively. For the patients, average levels of D-dimer, ferritin, LDH, IL-6 were **353 ng/ml**, **346 units/L**, **544.8 ug/ml**, **39.3 pg/ml** at the time of admission.

CT severity index was found to be in range of **13-15**.

Of **150** patients, **53(35%)** patients were with no comorbidities, **32(21%)** patients were of hypertension, **21(15%)** patients were with diabetes mellitus and **39(26%)** patients had both hypertension and diabetes mellitus. About **5(3%)** patients were with hypothyroidism.

NO COMORBIDITES

Out of **150** patients, **53** were without any comorbidities. Most of them were of gender male: **37** patients (**70%**) and rest of the **30%** were female: **16** patients.

There are **23** patients (**43%**) in the age range of 41-60 years while **18** patients (**34%**) were below 41 years and **12** patients (**23%**) were above 60 years of age.

Although, the patients were with no comorbidities, **57%** (**30** patients) of them had hospitalized for 8-14 days, whereas **18** patients (**34%**) hospitalized for less than a

week and **5** patients (**9%**) hospitalized for more than 2 weeks.

Only **30%** that is **16** patients required intensive care and rest of the **37** patients (**70%**) were treated in room.

Remdesivir was administered for **39** patients (**74%**) and Favipiravir was administered for **3** patients (**6%**) while **11** patients were not given anti-viral therapy.

Seven patients (**13%**) were given convalescent plasma therapy.

Out of **53** patients, **32** patients (**60%**) required 1-4 mg/kg of systemic steroid dose, whereas **10** patients (**19%**) required less than 1 mg/kg of steroid dose and **11** patients (**21%**) required more than 4 mg/kg of steroid dose.

Two patients (**4%**) required mechanical ventilation, **3** patients (**6%**) required oxygen through HFNC, **4** patients (**8%**) required oxygen through NIV and **7** patients (**13%**) required oxygen through oxygen mask.

The mean values of CRP at admission, during therapy and at discharge were **48.6 ug/ml**, **29.5 ug/ml**, **13.2 ug/ml** respectively. The average values of D-dimer, Ferritin, LDH, IL-6 of the patients at the time of admission were found to be **318.6 ng/ml**, **281.4 units/L**, **575.6 ug/ml**, **41.6 pg/ml**.

The CT severity index was **13** in majority of the patients. **6%** (**3** patients) mortality was observed while **94%** (**50** patients) were discharged after being stable.

HYPERTENSION

Out of **150** patients, **32** were with Hypertension. Most of them were of gender male.

24 patients (**75%**) and rest of the **25%** were female: **8** patients.

There are **10** patients (**31%**) in the age range of 41-60 years while **2** patients (**6%**) were below 41 years and **20** patients (**63%**) were above 60 years of age.

60% (**19** patients) of them had hospitalized for 8-14 days, whereas **10** patients (**31%**) hospitalized for less than a week and **3** patients (**9%**) hospitalized for more than 2 weeks.

Only **34%** that is **11** patients required intensive care and rest of the **21** patients (**66%**) were treated in room.

Remdesivir was administered for **25** patients (**78%**) and Favipiravir was administered for **1** patient (**3%**) while **6** patients were not given anti-viral therapy.

Seven patients (**22%**) were given convalescent plasma therapy.

Out of **32** patients, **22** patients (**69%**) required 1-4 mg/kg of systemic steroid dose, whereas **5** patients (**16%**) required less than 1 mg/kg of steroid dose and **5** patients (**16%**) required more than 4 mg/kg of steroid dose.

One patient (**3%**) required mechanical ventilation, **1** patient (**3%**) required oxygen through NIV and **14** patients (**44%**) required oxygen through oxygen mask.

The mean values of CRP at admission, during therapy and at discharge were **45.5 ug/ml**, **27.3 ug/ml**, **10.2 ug/ml** respectively.

The average values of D-dimer, Ferritin, LDH, IL-6 of the patients at the time of admission were found to

be **342.1 ng/ml, 299.3 units/L, 586.9 ug/ml, 23.5 pg/ml**. The CT severity index was **13** in majority of the patients. **3%** (1 patient) mortality was observed while **88%** (28 patients) were discharged after being stable and **9%** (3 patients) were referred to higher center.

DIABETES MELLITUS

Out of **150** patients, **21** were with Diabetes mellitus. Most of them were of gender male: **12** patients (**57%**) and rest of the **43%** were female: **9** patients.

There are **10** patients (**48%**) in the age range of 41-60 years while **11** patients (**52%**) were above 60 years of age.

62% (13 patients) of them had hospitalized for 8-14 days, whereas **3** patients (**14%**) hospitalized for less than a week and **5** patients (**24%**) hospitalized for more than 2 weeks.

Only **48%** that is **10** patients required intensive care and rest of the **11** patients (**52%**) were treated in room.

Remdesivir was administered for **16** patients (**76%**) and Favipiravir was administered for **1** patient (**5%**) while **4** patients were not given anti-viral therapy.

Three patients (**14%**) were given convalescent plasma therapy.

Out of **21** patients, **14** patients (**67%**) required 1-4 mg/kg of systemic steroid dose, whereas **4** patients (**19%**) required less than 1 mg/kg of steroid dose and **3** patients (**14%**) required more than 4 mg/kg of steroid dose.

Two patients (**10%**) required oxygen through NIV and **10** patients (**48%**) required oxygen through oxygen mask. The mean values of CRP at admission, during therapy and at discharge were **45.6 ug/ml, 30.1ug/ml, 18.9 ug/ml** respectively.

The average values of D-dimer, Ferritin, LDH, IL-6 of the patients at the time of admission were found to be **388 ng/ml, 307 units/L, 603 ug/ml, 74 pg/ml**.

The CT severity index was **14** in majority of the patients. **5%** (1 patient) mortality was observed while **90%** (19 patients) were discharged after being stable and **5%** (1 patient) was referred to higher center.

DIABETES MELLITUS + HYPERTENSION

Out of **150** patients, **39** were with Diabetes mellitus + Hypertension. Most of them were of gender male: **28** patients (**72%**) and rest of the **28%** were female: **11** patients.

There are **21** patients (**54%**) in the age range of 41-60 years while **18** patients (**46%**) were above 60 years of age. **77%** (30 patients) of them had hospitalized for 8-14 days, whereas **6** patients (**15%**) hospitalized for less than a week and **3** patients (**8%**) hospitalized for more than 2 weeks.

Only **36%** that is **14** patients required intensive care and rest of the **25** patients (**64%**) were treated in room.

Remdesivir was administered for **37** patients (**95%**) while **2** patients were not given anti-viral therapy.

Only **2** patients (**5%**) were given convalescent plasma therapy.

Out of **39** patients, **30** patients (**77%**) required 1-4 mg/kg of systemic steroid dose, whereas **5** patients (**13%**)

required less than 1 mg/kg of steroid dose and **4** patients (**10%**) required more than 4 mg/kg of steroid dose.

One patient (**3%**) required mechanical ventilation, **3** patients (**8%**) required oxygen through NIV and **19** patients (**49%**) required oxygen through oxygen mask.

The mean values of CRP at admission, during therapy and at discharge were **53.2ug/ml, 38.2 ug/ml, 25.9 ug/ml** respectively.

The average values of D-dimer, Ferritin, LDH, IL-6 of the patients at the time of admission were found to be **372 ng/ml, 265 units/L, 553 ug/ml, 35.9 pg/ml**. The CT severity index was **15** in majority of the patients.

3% (1 patient) mortality was observed while **82%** (32 patients) were discharged after being stable and **15%** (6 patients) were referred to higher center.

COMPARISION BETWEEN PATIENTS WITH NO COMORBIDITIES AND PATIENTS WITH HYPERTENSION

From our results, we found that patients with hypertension (**69%**) required longer hospital stay of above a week than those with no comorbidities (**66%**).

The patients with hypertension (**34%**) required intensive care more than patients with no comorbidities (**30%**). **85%** of patients with hypertension required more than 1mg/kg of steroid dose while **81%** of patients with no comorbidities were given more than 1mg/kg of steroids.

While **79%** of patients with no comorbidities were given anti-viral therapy, **81%** of patients with hypertension were given anti-viral therapy.

When compared to patients with no comorbidities where only **30%** required oxygenation through oxygen mask (**13%**), NIV (**7%**), HFNC (**6%**), Ventilator (**4%**), **50%** of patients with hypertension required oxygenation through oxygen mask (**44%**), NIV (**3%**) and ventilator (**3%**).

88% of patients with hypertension were discharged while **9%** were referred to higher centers and **3%** were expired whereas **94%** of patients with no comorbidities were discharged in stable condition and **6%** were expired.

COMPARISION BETWEEN PATIENTS WITH NO COMORBIDITIES AND PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

From our results, we found patients with diabetes mellitus (**86%**) required longer hospital stay of above a week than those with no comorbidities (**66%**).

The patients with diabetes mellitus (**48%**) required intensive care more than patients with no comorbidities (**30%**)

81% of patients with diabetes mellitus required more than 1mg/kg of steroid dose while **81%** of patients with no comorbidities were given more than 1mg/kg of steroids.

While **79%** of patients with no comorbidities were given anti-viral therapy, **81%** of patients with diabetes mellitus were given anti-viral therapy.

When compared to patients with no comorbidities where only 30% required oxygenation through oxygen mask (13%), NIV (7%), HFNC (6%), Ventilator (4%), 57% of patients with diabetes mellitus required oxygenation through oxygen mask (48%) and NIV (9%).

90% of patients with diabetes mellitus were discharged while 5% were referred to higher centers and 5% were expired whereas 94% of patients with no comorbidities were discharged in stable condition and 6% were expired.

COMPARISON BETWEEN PATIENTS WITH NO COMORBIDITIES AND PATIENTS WITH DIABETES MELLITUS + HYPERTENSION

From our results, we found that patients with diabetes mellitus + hypertension (85%) required longer hospital stay of above a week than those with no comorbidities (66%).

The patients with diabetes mellitus + hypertension (36%) required intensive care more than patients with no comorbidities (30%).

87% of patients with diabetes mellitus + hypertension required more than 1mg/kg of steroid dose while 81% of patients with no comorbidities were given more than 1mg/kg of steroids.

While 79% of patients with no comorbidities were given anti-viral therapy, 95% of patients with diabetes mellitus + hypertension was given.

When compared to patients with no comorbidities where only 30% required oxygenation through oxygen mask (13%), NIV (7%), HFNC (6%), Ventilator (4%), 60% of patients with diabetes mellitus + hypertension required oxygenation through oxygen mask (49%), NIV (7%) and ventilator (3%).

While 82% of patients with diabetes mellitus + hypertension were discharged, 15% were referred to higher centers and 3% were expired whereas 94% of patients with no comorbidities were discharged in stable condition and 6% were expired.

CONCLUSION: Our findings concluded that.

Compared with ordinary patients (patients with no comorbidities), patients with comorbidities were older, had higher proportion of men requiring longer hospital stay and time to cure.

Presence of comorbidities increased intensive care admissions.

Comparing with patients of no comorbidities, there are 4%, 18%, 6% more intensive care admissions for hypertension, diabetes mellitus, diabetes mellitus + hypertensive patients respectively.

The length of stay for patients with hypertension, diabetes mellitus, diabetes mellitus + hypertension was found to be 3%, 20%, 19% more than the length of stay for patients without comorbidities. As, steroids were used to suppress severe cytokine storm, use of high dose steroids resulted in increased blood glucose levels leading to hyperglycemic state, not only for those with diabetes mellitus but also for those patients having no history of diabetes.

Withdrawal of steroids from therapy may cause severe inflammatory reactions, hence by gradual tapering of doses and simultaneous monitoring and management of glucose levels with insulin and oral hypoglycemic agents showed better results and a good recovery.

This steroid induced hyperglycemia effect showed impact on longer clinical management and hospital stay. For patients with comorbidities, there was higher transfer out rate compared to patients with no comorbidities.

For mortality rate, there is no statistically significant difference as there are small number of deaths associated. However, comorbidities had no obvious impact on mortality rate but reduced the cure rate and prolonged the length of stay and clinical course of patients.

This study also sought to explore how various parameters effected the quality of life.

Measures To Improve Quality of Life

- Encouraging the patients to practice self-hygiene by regularly sanitizing their hands, using mask to avoid spread, maintaining social distance.
- Counseling the patients and care takers regarding disease and importance of using medication to prevent severity of disease.
- Family (especially the spouse) interventions and support can contribute to provide psychological support and strength to tackle with the pandemic stress.
- Therapies targeting the management of comorbidities like diabetes and hypertension should not affect the prognosis of COVID – 19 in patients.

Measures To Manage Hypertension Along With COVID – 19

- Regularly monitoring blood pressure levels.
- Encouraging to follow DASH diet.
- If patient is on ARBs or ACEIs, alternate therapy should be considered if required.
- Cut back on caffeine.
- Take prescribed medications regularly
- Reduce sodium
- Limit alcohol consumption
- Quit smoking
- Relax by meditating, yoga, deep breathing and reduce stress.

Measures To Manage Diabetes Mellitus Along With COVID – 19

- Regularly monitor blood glucose levels while on steroid therapy.
- Calculate accurate insulin doses by measuring blood glucose levels at regular intervals
- Reduce carbohydrate intake
- Take protein rich food.
- Limit the intake of fats, junk foods.
- Manage weight.
- Perform aerobic exercises or walking for at least half an hour.
- Stay hydrated
- Consume balanced diet

- Maintain adequate sleep

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